

Seroprevalence of Herpes Simplex Virus 1 and 2 at a Tertiary Care Centre of North IndiaMaasha¹, Sidhu SK², Singh K³, Kaur M⁴, Nagpal N⁵, Sidhu HS⁶¹Senior Resident, Department of Microbiology, Government Medical College, Amritsar, Punjab, India²Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Government Medical College, Amritsar, Punjab, India³Professor and Head, Department of Virology, Government Medical College, Amritsar, Punjab, India⁴Research Scientist (Medical), Department of Virology, Government Medical College, Amritsar, Punjab, India⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Government Medical College, Amritsar, Punjab, India⁶MBBS Student, MMU, Mulana, Ambala, India

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Abstract:

Background: Herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1) and type 2 (HSV-2) are common human pathogens. Most primary HSV-1 and HSV-2 infections are asymptomatic and self-limited, but can be complicated with fulminant diseases. Thus, this study has its own objective to determine the clinicoepidemiological profile of HSV (1 and 2) infections in the symptomatic patients whose blood samples were received at the department of Virology, Government medical college Amritsar.

Methods: A total of 231 samples were included in our study from the month of August 2023 to August 2024. All the samples fulfilling the inclusion criteria were subjected for ELISA.

Results: Out of 231 samples, 52 (22.51%) were HSV (1-2) IgM positive and 154 (66.66%) were HSV (1-2) IgG positive. Females (52.38%) were predominantly infected showing more positivity of HSV (1-2) than males (36.79%). Maximum number of cases (108) were from age group 21-40 years. Amongst this age group, 34 (65.38%) were positive for HSV (1-2) IgM and 74 (48.05%) for HSV (1-2) IgG. The patients presented with various complaints like genital lesions, orolabial lesions, redness, swelling, pain/itching, painful urination and vaginal discharge, headache, malaise, fever and muscle aches.

Conclusion: The purpose of screening for HSV is not only to identify seropositivity, but to help seropositive people identify symptoms and protect themselves from acquiring further complications and to protect their partners and seronegative people from acquiring HSV.

Keywords: Herpes Simplex Virus, Seroprevalence, ELISA, IgM, IgG.

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Introduction

Infection with Herpes Simplex Virus (HSV) is one of the world's most common sexually transmitted diseases that is categorized into HSV- type 1 (HSV-1) and HSV- type 2 (HSV-2). HSV has a great impact on human health globally due to its high prevalence, successful sexual transmissibility rate, association with Immunocompromised patients, and ability to cause recurrent disease.[1]

Herpes Simplex Viruses are double- stranded DNA viruses belonging to Herpesviridae family.[2] HSV-1 is transmitted through oral contact and HSV-2 is transmitted through sexual contact.[3]. When symptoms occur, they consist primarily of episodic ulcerative lesions at the site of infection. Both viruses are capable of causing either anogenital or orolabial infection and can produce primary

and recurrent lesions that are clinically indistinguishable.[4] HSV-1 infection typically causes orolabial lesions, and HSV-2 typically causes genital lesions.[5]. Symptomatic infections might lead to central nervous system manifestations (e.g., meningitis and encephalitis), corneal blindness, and death, especially among immunocompromised patients.[6] Following primary infection, HSV establishes latency in nerve ganglia; i.e. HSV-1 in the trigeminal ganglion, and HSV-2 in the sacral ganglion. The infection can become recurrent on a periodic basis due to virus reactivation.[2]

According to World Health Organization (WHO) survey, an estimated 3.8 billion people under age 50 (64.2%) globally have herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1) infection, and an estimated 519.5 mil-

lion people aged 15–49 (13.3%) worldwide have herpes simplex virus type 2 (HSV-2) infection. [7] Following HSV infection, variable time is required for the development of immunoglobulin M (IgM) and G (IgG) antibodies after the onset of symptoms. Most individuals can have anti-HSV-1-2 IgM detected 9 - 10 days following exposure to the virus and it can be detectable for up to 6 weeks. Anti-HSV 1-2 IgG takes 14-90 days to develop after onset of symptoms and persists indefinitely.[6] These antibodies can be detected by various immunological methods. Advancements in the serological methods such as ELISA have made it feasible to measure HSV 1-2 IgM and IgG antibodies and provide an epidemiological evaluation of the burden of HSV infection.[2] Seroprevalence studies assist researchers and legislators in developing efficacious strategies for the prevention and control of the spread of this virus. Thus, in present study we aimed to evaluate the seroprevalence of HSV-1 and HSV-2 at a tertiary care hospital.

Material and Methods

This retrospective study was conducted in the department of Virology at Government Medical College, Amritsar, and Punjab on 231 patients from the period of August 2023 to August 2024. The study included all the patients who presented with com-

plaints of painful blisters around the mouth or in genital area along with fever, sore throat and body aches. All the samples were properly labelled and particulars of the patients along with demographic details and presenting complaints were recorded on a pre-designed proforma and enclosed with samples. Approximately 7-8 ml venous blood sample was collected in vacutainer from each patient under strict aseptic precautions and transported in cold chain to department of Virology at Government Medical College Amritsar. Sera was obtained by centrifuging the blood for 8 min at 3000 rpm. Samples were then stored at -20 deg C till assay was carried out. The serum samples were then subjected to Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) for HSV (1-2) IgM antibodies detection by using Qualisa HSV (1,2) IgM kit and HSV (1-2) IgG antibodies detection by using Qualisa HSV (1,2) IgG kit according to manufacturer's instructions and results were interpreted as described by the kit. Blank, negative, and positive controls were included with each run. The cut-off value was optical density (OD) ≥ 0.25 .

Results

A total of 231 samples were tested, out of which 52 (22.51%) were HSV (1-2) IgM positive and 154 (66.66%) were HSV (1-2) IgG positive.

Figure 1: Prevalence of HSV (1-2) IgM and HSV (1-2) IgG.

Amongst the total 231 cases, 105 were males and 126 were females who were included in the study. Positivity for HSV (1,2) in females 121(52.38%) was higher than in males 85 (36.79%).

Figure 2: Gender wise distribution of positive cases.

Maximum number of positive cases (108) were from age group 21-40 years. Amongst this age group 34 (14.71%) were positive for HSV (1-2) IgM and 74 (67.88%) for HSV (1-2) IgG.

Table 3: Age wise distribution of cases

Age Group	Total	HSV 1-2 IgM positive (n=52)	HSV 1-2 IgG positive (n=154)
≤10 years	21	1 (1.92%)	20 (12.98%)
11-20 years	25	11 (21.15%)	14 (9.09%)
21-40 years	108	34 (65.38%)	74 (48.05%)
41-60 years	38	5 (9.61%)	33 (21.42%)
≥60 years	14	1 (1.92%)	13 (8.44%)

When we analysed the presenting symptoms, number of genital lesions [156 (67.53%)] were highest amongst all the cases followed by orolabial lesions [96 (41.55%)].

Local symptoms like redness [79 (34.19%)], swelling [74 (32%)], pain/itching [68 (29.43%)], painful

urination [58 (25.10%)] and vaginal discharge [45 (19.48%)] were present.

Systemic symptoms like headache [97 (41.99%)], malaise [124 (53.67%)], fever [112 (48.48%)] and muscle aches [86 (37.22%)] were found in most of the patients.

Figure 3: Symptoms

Discussion

Herpes simplex virus is quite common throughout the world. HSV causes infection in oral as well as genital area in the lesion form as well as local and systemic manifestations. The clinical diagnosis of herpes is both insensitive and non-specific. Only approximately 20% of herpes infections have classic vesicular or ulcerative lesions. The clinical diagnosis can be confirmed by laboratory testing using culture, direct antigen tests, PCR, Cytology and type-specific serologies. [8].

This retrospective study confirms and extends several observations of HSV (1,2) infection. It applies the clinical presentation of HSV (1,2) and its serological diagnosis. We included all the cases presenting with symptoms of HSV as per WHO criteria.[7]. It was observed that seroprevalence of IgG HSV (1,2) (66.66%) was more than IgM HSV (1,2) (22.51%). Venkateshwaran SP et al also showed in their study that there was higher rate of HSV 1-2 IgG (80%, 60%) than HSV 1-2 IgM (60%, 28.6%) [1]. A similar study by Amar OAO et al also showed higher rate of HSV IgG (64.9%) than HSV IgM (2.1%).[9]. Similar results were seen in a study by Taherpoor et al.[2]. This suggested a high prevalence of latent infection in the population. [4] This implies that these individuals have been infected with the virus and had developed antibodies, hence are carriers of the virus. [10].

In present study, on analysis of gender wise distribution, both HSV (1,2) IgM and HSV (1,2) IgG were found higher in females (11.25%, 37.22%) than males (6.06%, 29.43%). A study by Taherpool et al also showed that there was a higher rate of HSV (1,2) IgG in females (64.3%) than in males (35.7%).[2]. V.P. Amudha et al. in their study also revealed that more females (36.84%) than males (34.62%) tested positive with HSV antibodies. [8]. McQuillan G also showed that prevalence of HSV (1,2) antibodies was higher in females (50.9%) than males. (45.2%) [11].

Even CDC reports that HSV-2 infection is more common among women than men (20.9% versus 11.5%). It has been postulated that the increased seroprevalence of HSV in women is the result of more efficient male-to-female transmission of the virus, anatomical differences in susceptibility to infection, or the tendency of women to choose sex partners who are older than themselves. [12]. Females as compared to males have tendency of more number and early sero conversion [13]. Another probable explanation for the high prevalence of HSV in the female participant could be related to the anatomy of the female reproductive system. That is, the large surface area and the thin lining of the female reproductive system could facilitate HSV-2 entry. [14]. Also, due to larger affected surface area in women and ability of the virus to

spread more easily over moist surfaces, women have more severe disease, constitutional symptoms, and complications than men [15]. When we analysed the age group, we found out that maximum number of HSV (1,2) IgM and HSV (1,2) IgG positive cases were from age group 21-40 years (14.71%, 67.88% resp). Similarly, two studies reported the predominance of HSV seropositivity in a younger age group (21 - 40 years) [16,17]. This was also in concordance with a study done by Jalil MB et al. [18]. The occurrence in this age group may be related to the increased sexual activity with the advancement of age, since sexual contact is one of the main routes of virus transmission[2]. This age group not only have highest prevalence of infection, but likely also contribute an important burden of disease in terms of continuing recurrences. [19]. Latest analyses have addressed the issue regarding the substantial burden of HSV in young adults in the developed countries. Public health hazards could arise along with this epidemiological situation. Firstly, genital herpes could be associated with an increased risk of HIV infections. Secondly, pregnant women who acquire primary genital herpes might transmit HSV to newborns during labor and delivery and neonatal HSV infections have a high risk of severe morbidity.[20]

All the cases in this study presented with different clinical manifestations. Irrespective of the clinical type, most recognized disease was genital (67.53%) followed by orolabial lesions (41.55%). Local symptoms like redness (34.19%), swelling (32%), pain/itching (29.43%), painful urination (25.10%) and vaginal discharge (19.48%) were present. Others had only systemic symptoms like headache (41.99%), malaise (53.67%), fever (48.48%) and muscle aches (37.22%). In a similar study, primary first-episode genital herpes was accompanied by systemic symptoms (67%), local pain and itching (98%), dysuria (63%), and tender adenopathy (80%) and also the patients presented with several bilaterally distributed pustular ulcerative lesions. [21.]. David IB also reported similar symptoms like genital lesions, painful urination, vaginal discharge, redness, swelling, fever, headache, malaise and muscle aches. [22].

After an incubation period of 1–26 days, classical primary genital herpes begins with prodromal symptoms characterized by localized pain or tingling lasting up to 24 hours. Constitutional symptoms like fever, headache, malaise and inguinal lymphadenopathy are accompanied further. Papules followed by vesicles and pustules and later erosions appear over hours to days. These lesions usually crust and then re-epithelialise and heal without scarring.[23] The frequency of HSV infection has been measured by testing various populations for the presence of antibody, as both virus and the immune response are thought to persist after infection

for the life of the host.[24]. Although infections in individuals without prior exposure to either virus (primary infections) may often be subclinical, they tend to be more severe than infections occurring in individuals previously exposed to HSV-1 and/or HSV-2. [25].

HSV can lead to various complications. It increases the risk of acquiring HIV infection by approximately three-fold. Rare complications of HSV-2 include meningoencephalitis and disseminated infection. Rarely, HSV-1 infection can lead to more severe complications such as encephalitis or keratitis. [7].

Finally, it is difficult to distinguish HSV infections from other diseases that cause similar signs and symptoms by clinical examination, and thus serology is recommended as an aid to the clinician. [22]. After primary infection, HSV-2 spreads in a retrograde manner to the sensory ganglia and establishes a latent infection. The virus may reactivate and induce asymptomatic viral shedding or recurrent infections [13]. Recurrence can be increased by several factors, such as immunodeficiency and the severity and length of the primary episode. Even persons with first-episode herpes who have mild clinical manifestations initially can experience severe or prolonged symptoms during recurrent infections. Therefore, all patients with first episodes of genital herpes should receive antiviral therapy. [26].

Conclusion

In summary, the results of the present study showed that the prevalence of HSV significantly increases with age when sexual activity starts. Health providers should therefore include in their counselling of adolescents information about HSV and behavioural acquisition risks with the goal to prevent herpes infections, and thus also its complications. Other findings also have important implications for the design and implementation of treatment and prevention strategies. [22] HSV infections by either type were most often not recognized by the participants, despite the efforts to educate those regarding possible signs and symptoms of HSV disease. Thus, continuing surveillance for the epidemiology, the route of transmission, and the implementation of public health strategies are highly recommended. [20]

References

1. Venkateshwaran SP, Murugesan K, Sivaraj R. Seroprevalence of Ig G and Ig M antibodies in individuals with herpes simplex virus-1 & 2 infection in HIV positive and negative individuals of South Indian population. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*. 2011 Dec 30; 1(10):154-8.
2. Taherpoor A, Vojdani A, Hashemi SM, Amali A, Mardani MR, Mobarhan MG, Esmaily H,

- Shakeri MT, Bakhshi M, Meshkat M, Chechaklou AH. Seroprevalence of Herpes Simplex Viruses Types 1 and 2 in a Population, Age 15-35 Years, of Mashhad City. *Iranian biomedical journal*. 2023 Mar; 27(2-3):152.
3. Ahmed H, Abbu N, Saeed S, Abdalla W, Mohammed Salih K, Abd Alla A, Hashim A. Seroprevalence of herpes simplex virus type-2 among pregnant women in Wad Madani-Sudan: a cross-sectional study. *F1000 Research*. 2022 Jul 6; (11):752.
4. Xu F, Schillinger JA, Sternberg MR, Johnson RE, Lee FK, Nahmias AJ, Markowitz LE. Seroprevalence and coinfection with herpes simplex virus type 1 and type 2 in the United States, 1988–1994. *The Journal of infectious diseases*. 2002 Apr 15; 185(8):1019-24.
5. Bradley H, Markowitz LE, Gibson T, McQuillan GM. Seroprevalence of herpes simplex virus types 1 and 2—United States, 1999–2010. *The Journal of infectious diseases*. 2014 Feb 1; 209(3):325-33.
6. Taha AE, Ghazy AA, Almaeen A, Taher I, El-Metwally T, Alayyaf MA, Alrayes F, Alinad A, Albulayhid S, Aldakhil A. Estimation of Seroprevalence of Anti-Herpes Simplex Virus Type-1 IgG Among Healthy Blood Donors in Sakaka City, Aljouf, Saudi Arabia. *Jundishapur Journal of Microbiology*. 2023 Jul 31; 16(7).
7. World Health Organization. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/herpes-simplex-virus#:~:text=Key facts,main cause of genital herpes.> (Accessed: 13 September 2024).
8. Amudha VP, Rashetha, Sucilathangam G, Cinthujah B, Revathy C. Serological Profile of HSV-2 in STD patients : Evaluation of Diagnostic utility of HSV-2 IgM and IgG Detection. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*. 2014 Dec, Vol-8(12): DC16-DC19
9. Amar OA, Bajaj HK, Gupta N, Singla A, Masih H. Prevalence of herpes simplex virus in pregnant women from gangetic plain region of Allahabad, India. *Advances in Microbiology*. 2015 Jun 2; 5(6):404-8.
10. Hayatudeen MR, Mukhtar GL, Aminu M. Seroprevalence of Immunoglobulins G and M Associated With Herpes Simplex Virus Type 2 among Apparently Healthy Individuals in Katsina State, Nigeria. *UMYU Journal of Microbiology Research (UJMR)*. 2017 Jun 30; 2(1):186-91.
11. McQuillan G, Kruszon-Moran D, Flagg EW, Paulose-Ram R. Prevalence of herpes simplex virus type 1 and type 2 in persons aged 14-49: United States, 2015-2016.
12. Doi Y, Ninomiya T, Hata J, Yonemoto K, Tanizaki Y, Arima H, Liu Y, Rahman M, Iida M, Kiyohara Y. Seroprevalence of herpes simplex

- virus 1 and 2 in a population-based cohort in Japan. *Journal of epidemiology*. 2009 Mar 5; 19(2):56-62.
13. Tada DG, Khandelwal N. Serum HSV-1 and 2 IgM in Sexually Transmitted Diseases-More for Screening Less for Diagnosis: An Evaluation of Clinical Manifestation. *Journal of Global Infectious Diseases*. 2012 Jul 1; 4(3):S1-4.
 14. Obisesan OS, Sithebe NP, Mufhandu HT. Seroprevalence and characterisation of Herpes Simplex Virus from human immunodeficiency virus in samples collected from two provinces in South Africa : a retrospective study [version 4; peer review : 2 approved]. *F1000 Research*. 17 Nov 2021; 10:105
 15. Beauman JG. Genital herpes: a review. *American family physician*. 2005 Oct 15; 72(8):1527-34.
 16. Khudair Kh, Ibrahim Al- kayalli, Mohammed K, Khudair Al- Azawy, Ammar T, Nasser Al-Azawy. Evaluation of seroprevalence of herpes simplex virus IgG antibody in Baquba city by using ELISA technique. *Diyala Journal for Pure Sciences*; Mpril 2015; 11 (2)
 17. Al-Shuwaikh AM, Hanna DB, Ali ZQ. Seroprevalence of Herpes Simplex Virus Type-1 IgG Antibody in Healthy Blood Donor from Baghdad, Iraq. *Journal of Pure & Applied Microbiology*. 2019 Jun 1; 13(2).
 18. Mays JB, Basil MJ, Mariem MA, Alabadi HI. Seroprevalence of herpes simplex virus type 1 (Herpesviridae: Simplexvirus: Human alphaherpesvirus 1) in smokers. *Problems of Virology*. 2024 May 6; 69(2):187-92.
 19. James C, Harfouche M, Welton NJ, Turner KM, Abu-Raddad LJ, Gottlieb SL, Looker KJ. Herpes simplex virus: global infection prevalence and incidence estimates, 2016. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2020 May 5; 98(5):315.
 20. Shen JH, Huang KY, Chao-Yu C, Chen CJ, Lin TY, Huang YC. Seroprevalence of herpes simplex virus type 1 and 2 in Taiwan and risk factor analysis, 2007. *PloS one*. 2015 Aug 7; 10(8):e0134178.
 21. Corey L, Adams HG, Brown ZA, Holmes KK. Genital herpes simplex virus infections: clinical manifestations, course, and complications. *Annals of internal medicine*. 1983 Jun 1; 98(6):958-72.
 22. Bernstein DI, Bellamy AR, Hook III EW, Levin MJ, Wald A, Ewell MG, Wolff PA, Deal CD, Heineman TC, Dubin G, Belshe RB. Epidemiology, clinical presentation, and antibody response to primary infection with herpes simplex virus type 1 and type 2 in young women. *Clinical infectious diseases*. 2013 Feb 1; 56(3):344-51.
 23. Azwa A, Barton SE. Aspects of herpes simplex virus: a clinical review. *BMJ Sexual & Reproductive Health*. 2009 Oct 1; 35(4):237.
 24. Wald A, Corey L. Persistence in the population: epidemiology, transmission. *Human herpesviruses: biology, therapy, and immunoprophylaxis*. 2007.
 25. Nahmias AJ, Josey WE. Epidemiology of herpes simplex viruses 1 and 2. In *Viral infections of humans: Epidemiology and control 1976* (pp. 253-271). Boston, MA: Springer US.
 26. Herbin C, Jadoul P, Hosten E, Gerday A, Luyckx M, Squifflet JL, Perlepe V, Maillard C. Atypical presentation of herpes simplex virus 2 primary infection: a case report. *Journal of Medical Case Reports*. 2024 Aug 25; 18(1):393.